

MODEL FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of a model for the development of creative competence in non-philological students in the process of teaching English. Through this model, the results and stages of developing creative competence in teaching English in the educational process are discussed.

Keywords: English language teaching, creative competence, model, methodology, stages, preparation, universality.

Analysis of pedagogical research has led to the conclusion that there is no single approach to the classification of educational models. But all of them are based on the main categories of pedagogy: education, upbringing, teaching. For example, E.A.Lodatko believes that a model of the education system can be understood as a conceptual approach to building an education system, according to which "concepts about the effectiveness and values of educational institutions are formed based on management positions" [1]. Based on this definition, and also based on the research results of V.P. Bepalko, B.S. Gershunskiy, A.N. Daxin, V.V. Krayevskiy, V.M. Yatrovskaya, and others, the following types of professional education models can be distinguished: optimizing the organization of education management; education; the educational process; and the results of the educational process.

Within the framework of the research, the goal was set to develop a model for developing creative competence in English language lessons.

When developing a special model for the research problem, the following tasks were solved:

Identify methodological approaches to developing a model for developing students' competencies.

2) Determine the components and structure of the model;

3) show the relationship between the components and elements of the model;

4) Describe the component structure and elements of the model. The above-mentioned set of goals and objectives for the development of students' creative activity is related to methodological approaches.

In the process of teaching English, we use the modeling method (we will describe the educational model) to create a holistic understanding of the gradual development of creative competence in non-philology students, that is, the study of objects and phenomena using their conventional images and analogues [3]. In this context, the educational model is understood as "a logically sequential system of relevant elements, including educational goals, educational content, pedagogical technology, and the design of educational process management technology, as well as curricula and programs" [4].

In the process of teaching English, a systematic principle has been established based on the model for developing the creative competence of non-philology students. This takes into account the specialization, the specifics of the educational institution, the pedagogical conditions of training for the development of professional competencies, and the internal and external factors of vocational education.

In our research, we rely on the perspective of S.I. Ojegov, who views the concept of "condition" as "a condition related to something, a condition in which something is effectively implemented" [5]. Pedagogical conditions are understood as conditions related to pedagogical activity, which determine something in a particular process, that is, the set of factors ensuring the success of teaching, the components of the educational process (the purposeful selection, design, and application of elements of content, methods (techniques), as well as organizational forms of teaching).

When developing a model for developing creative competence in non-philology students in the process of teaching English, we adhered to the general requirements for creating models proposed by A.M. Novikov and D.A. Novikov: the coherence, simplicity, and adequacy of the model [6]. In our case, the model being implemented ensures sufficient compatibility with the educational environment in which it should operate, that is, the development of future teachers' creative competence in the process of teaching English. The simplicity of the model is achieved by selecting the most important properties of the modeled object, which ensures the ease of working with the model and its understanding by other researchers. The consistency of the model made it possible to achieve the set goals with its help, which implies the correspondence of the model to the purpose of its construction.

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